

Impact of Electrode Geometry on Stress Evolution and Crack Formation in Solid-State Batteries: Prediction and Experimental Validation

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Abstract

All-solid-state lithium-ion batteries (ASSLIBs) emerge as a promising next-generation technology, yet their realization is hindered by challenges, such as electrode/solid-electrolyte (SE) interface issues. Here, a combined experimental-computational approach is utilized to analyze the interplay between the geometrical structure of the electrode/SE interface configuration and electro-chemo-mechanical processes in an ASSLIB cell. Two types of physics-based models, which differ on the level of Multiphysics description, are developed: a pure electrochemical and a fully coupled electro-chemo-mechanical framework, to quantitatively compare their ability to predict experimentally observed ASSLIB behavior. The fully coupled model shows a strong agreement with experimental data, achieving less than 0.5% capacity difference at the end of discharge, while the pure model significantly deviates from experimental data, overestimating capacity by 26.5%. This underscores the importance of accounting for mechanical phenomena and Multiphysics coupling for accurate prediction. Following this validation, the coupled model is utilized to evaluate the impact of the planar and patterned (nonplanar) interface geometries on ASSLIB performance. It is observed that the patterned interface structure at/ near the pattern edges experiences the maximum gradient of lithium concentration and mechanical stress profiles. This is due to the sharp change in geometry, indicating a higher risk of mechanical failure, which is also experimentally confirmed as a critical area for crack formation. This study further investigates how variations in pattern geometric parameters affect ASSLIB performance, aiming to quantify the impact of pattern height, width, inter-distance, and base layer height. The results provide an in-depth analysis of the relationship between interface geometry type, lithium concentration, and stress profiles, offering guidance for optimizing geometric factors to limit mechanical failure.

Keywords:

Battery Performance Prediction, Mechanical Stress, Multiphysics simulation, Pattern geometry, planar geometry, crack formation

1. Introduction

All-solid-state lithium-ion batteries (ASSLIBs) are a next-generation rechargeable energy storage technology proposed to overcome the limitations of the current commercially available lithium-ion batteries^[1,2]. By utilizing a solid-state electrolyte (SE) instead of the flammable and volatile liquid electrolytes in conventional Lithium-ion Batteries (LIBs), ASSLIBs achieve a lighter weight, reduced volume, extended lifespan, enhanced safety, and higher energy density^[2,3]. These advantages result from the integration of SE with high-voltage, high-capacity electrodes. For instance, pairing a SE with a lithium-metal negative electrode, which has low density and the lowest redox potential (-3.04 V versus the standard hydrogen electrode (SHE)), boosts gravimetric and volumetric energy densities^[4]. Additionally, SE combined with high high-voltage positive electrode offers a substantial increase in theoretical energy density^[5,6].

Despite these promising properties, realizing the full potential of ASSLIBs is still challenging. While significant progress is being made, a number of challenges have yet to be overcome before the technology will be ready for practical use. Among these, electrode/SE interface issues are considered critical bottlenecks^[7-14]. The rigidity of the solid-state materials (electrolyte and electrodes) limits their full contact, resulting in poor electrochemical-mechanical compatibility between them. This impedes the lithium-ion (Li^+) transport and causes performance loss^[15,16]. During cycling, stress-induced cracking and increased interfacial impedance, especially at the SE/positive electrode interfaces, lead to rapid capacity decline and shortened lifespan^[17]. Addressing these interface issues is essential to unlocking the durability and high performance of ASSLIBs. However, the non-linear interaction among electro-chemo-mechanical processes driving degradation at these interfaces remains poorly understood^[15]. Experimental challenges add further complexity, as probing dynamic changes at the buried electrode/SE interfaces is difficult with ex-situ techniques^[18,19]. In-situ and operando methods reveal valuable insights into the composition and structural evolutions, yet linking electrochemical reactions, electro-chemo-mechanical processes, and degradation factors remains limited^[15,20,21]. In this context, high-fidelity numerical modeling can complement experimental techniques, offering deeper insights into these interconnected processes and aiding in the optimization of experimental designs.

At the macroscopic scale, continuum models have been instrumental in understanding and designing ASSLIBs and their associated electro-chemo-mechanical processes, as they bridge the gap between atomistic and macroscopic observations, offering valuable insights into battery behavior at relevant length and time scales. Becker-Steinberger et al.^[22] pioneered the development of a simplified 1D electrochemical model of ASSLIB that considered only Li^+ transport through the SE to the intercalation electrode, aiming to predict battery performance. This foundational model served as the basis for later, more comprehensive models by researchers such as Danilov et al.^[23], Fabre et al.^[24], and Tian et al.^[25] expanded the initial model by incorporating additional electrochemical phenomena, such as SE ionization and electron transport, to achieve a more detailed understanding of performance behavior. Building on this, Tian et al.^[25] incorporated imperfect interface contacts into a 1D Newman battery model to explore the effect of loss of interfacial contact area and found a correlation between capacity drop and contact area loss, which is almost linear at low cutoff voltages while nonlinear at higher cutoff voltages. Grazioli et al.^[26] and Shao et al.^[27] advanced these models by incorporating mechanical stress and studying the impact of contact loss and compressive pressure, with Grazioli et al.^[26] noting a significant impact of stress on electrochemical performance, and Shao et al.^[27] identified an optimal range for compressive pressure. On the other hand, Bates et al.^[28] developed a 2D model to study lithium-ion concentration distribution across the electrode's dimensions, while the Nadeau et al.^[29] 2D model examined the effect of geometric defects on stripping rate, particularly at high discharge rates.

Although these 2D models contributed valuable insights into the electrochemical process and the role of geometry, they did not incorporate mechanical stresses, which are critical to addressing ASSLIB failure.

Furthermore, in literature, some studies adopt geometries beyond traditional 1D and 2D planar designs, such as in 2D axisymmetric geometry, ASSLIBs with one electrode planar and another nonplanar structure architectures^[30–32]. Talin et al. ^[30] combined experimental fabrication of 3D microcolumn cells with finite element simulation, developing an electrochemical model to investigate how structural inhomogeneity impacts performance. Specifically, they used a 2D axisymmetric geometry in their finite element model, defined based on the conical-shaped elements observed in cross-sectional images of the 3D ASSLIB. Their results showed that while 3D architectures can increase areal capacity, non-uniform current distribution and limited ionic conductivity in the cathode led to underutilization and reduced power density. Ashby et al.^[31] developed an electrochemical model using a mixed 2D and 3D architecture, where the cathode consists of a 3D array of micro-pillars and the anode is planar, simulating ionic and electronic transport within the structured battery. Their main findings show that incorporating a high-conductivity SE is essential for achieving both high areal capacity and high-power density in this nonplanar design. Tian et al.^[32] extended the Talin et al. ^[30] electrochemical model by incorporating mechanical aspects, developing a one-way coupled electro-chemo-mechanical model to quantify stress evolution resulting from electrode volume changes and SE decomposition. They found that significant stress can be generated from SE decomposition. However, these studies did not link the nonplanar geometry variations to the electro-chemo-mechanical performances and efficiency.

To the best of our knowledge, a summary and comparison of the most relevant literature, highlighting different geometries and model types, is presented in Table 1. Those studies focus on either planar or nonplanar electrode geometries, without providing a comprehensive comparison across planar and nonplanar architectures. Quantifying the sensitivities of nonplanar (pattern) design parameters, such as pattern height, width, and inter-distance, and their effect on key performance indicators (KPIs) is rare, and experimental validation remains limited. Furthermore, they typically use either pure electrochemical or electro-chemo-mechanical models, while assuming static material properties. In practice, transport, kinetics, and mechanical parameters evolve dynamically during operation, influencing overall performance ^[33]. This demonstrates as such the need for integrated approaches to understand the complex interplay of electrochemical, mechanical, and geometric interactions under realistic dynamic conditions, supporting the design of more resilient battery architectures.

Table 1. Comparative overview of some selected physics-based modeling studies on ASSLIBs

References	Geometry type	Battery type	Parametrization technique		Mechanical degradation	Geometric parameter sensitivity analysis	KPI oriented	Validation
			Diffusion	Youngs modules				
This study	2D planar and pattern	Thin film	Dynamic, SoD dependent	Dynamic, SoD dependent	Yes	Several	Yes	Experimental
^[33]	2D planar	Thin film	Dynamic, SoD dependent	Dynamic, SoD dependent	Yes	No	Yes	Experimental/literature
^[23]	1D planar	Thin film	Static	-	No	No	No	Experimental
^[28]	2D planar	Thin film	Static	-	-	No	No	-

[34]	1D	Thin film	Static	Static	Yes	No	No	Literature
[35]	2D planar	Thin film	Static	Static	Yes	No	No	Experimental
[36]	1D	Thin film	Dynamic, SoD dependent	-	No	No	No	Experimental
[37]	2D planar	Composite	Dynamic, SoD dependent	Static	Yes	No	No	Literature
[38]	1D	Thin film	Temperature-dependent	static	Yes	No	No	Experimental
[30]	2D axisymmetric (conical cross section)	Thin film	Static	-	No	No	No	Experimental
[32]	2D axisymmetric (conical cross section)	Thin film	Static	Static	Yes	No	No	Literature
[31]	2D axisymmetric (pillar cross-section)	Composite	Static	-	No	No	No	experimental

In this study, we present a combined experimental-computational study of ASSLIBs, integrating fabrication, electrochemical testing, and continuum physics-based simulation, establishing a direct link between experimental observations and simulation-based predictions. Two models are developed to quantitatively compare their predictive accuracy and provide mechanistic insight into ASSLIBs behavior: (i) a pure electrochemical model that captures only electrochemical processes, excluding any mechanical effects, such as ion transport, charge transfer, and interfacial kinetics; and (ii) a fully coupled electro-chemo-mechanical model that simultaneously accounts for both electrochemical and mechanical processes, capturing their direct interactions. The model development builds upon our prior work^[33], where we established the critical role of dynamic parameters, such as state-of-discharge (SoD) dependent lithium-ion diffusivity and Young's modulus, in accurately capturing the complex behavior of active materials during battery operation. Both models are validated against experimental data obtained from a planar thin-film configuration and are subsequently extended to a patterned configuration to investigate geometric effects. By evaluating key physical characteristics and KPIs, our study provides insights into the complex relationships between these geometry configurations and ASSLIB performance. It reveals that pattern-type architectures exhibit pronounced geometry-driven stress concentrations, with mechanical crack hotspots forming preferentially at the pattern edges, within the pattern core, and at the pattern-base junction, especially when the pattern height exceeds the base-layer height. SEM characterization of cycled cells qualitatively confirms these predicted hotspot locations, confirming the model's ability to capture critical failure-prone regions. Together, these results establish a predictive framework for understanding geometry-dependent damage initiation and for guiding the design of more mechanically resilient solid-state battery architectures.

2. Computational Methods

2.1 Geometric Configuration

This work develops a physics-based continuum modelling framework to quantitatively analyze the impact of the electrode/SE interface geometrical configuration on ASSLIB performance and to identify hotspot areas for material failure. However, practical ASSLIBs utilized in applications such as electric

vehicles are inherently complex composite systems, consisting of multi-phase active materials, SE, binders, and conductive additives complexly arranged in heterogeneous microstructures with numerous solid–solid interfaces. This complexity poses substantial challenges for the development of comprehensive predictive models capable of capturing their intricate Multiphysics phenomena that dictate battery performance. However, its success depends on clearly defined governing physics, coupling mechanisms, modelling assumptions, and, critically, accurate input parameters. Many of these parameters, such as lithium diffusivity and interfacial properties, are highly material- and composition-dependent. Direct derivation of these parameters from fully complex systems is hindered by their structural heterogeneity, compositional variability, and multiscale characteristics, undermining the models' predictive fidelity.

To address this critical gap, we propose a hierarchical experiment-modeling strategy that progressively builds model systems of increasing complexity. Rather than immediately confronting the full complexity of composite electrodes, we start with a well-defined model system, specifically thin-film cells. These thin films provide a controlled structure with minimal morphological heterogeneity, enabling precise experimental characterization and parameter determination under clearly defined conditions. From this foundational baseline, we systematically evolve the model system by incrementally increasing geometric and compositional complexity, advancing toward practical composite electrodes that feature multiphase morphologies, heterogeneous interfaces, and microstructures. This staged approach supports the isolation and understanding of fundamental mechanisms while progressively integrating Multiphysics couplings and structural intricacies relevant to complex composite ASSLIBs. The evolution of complexity from thin films to composites is schematically illustrated in our previous study^[33], highlighting the deliberate pathway from simple to complex architectures. The system complexity is incrementally increased by introducing more realistic geometric features and compositional diversity, culminating in composite electrode architectures that incorporate multiphase materials, heterogeneous interfaces, and microstructural intricacies typical of practical ASSLIBs. This stepwise approach enables systematic parameter determination, model validation, and Multiphysics coupling, bridging the gap between idealized and real-world battery systems.

Moreover, this hierarchical experiment-modeling framework and associated modeling development address the key limitation of existing FEM models for ASSLIBs, the lack of experimentally validated parameters that correctly represent complex composite systems. By bridging from thin films to complex composites through well-characterized intermediate stages, we aim to enhance the predictive capability of Multiphysics simulations. This approach ultimately facilitates informed materials design, improved understanding of degradation mechanisms, and the accelerated development of durable, high-performance all-solid-state batteries.

For this study, an experimental-modeling framework was developed on the basis of thin-film types for two geometrical configurations, as depicted in Figure 1(a) and Figure 1(b), to systematically investigate structure–performance relationships in ASSLIBs.

Figure 1:(a-b) Evolution of experiment-modeling framework system complexity from planar (a) to patterned (b) thin film based ASSLIB architecture. h_{LMO} and h_{LiPON} indicate the height of the LMO electrode and LiPON SE, respectively, for the planar design. On the other hand, $h_{\text{LMO Base layer}}$ and $h_{\text{LiPON Base layer}}$ denote the height of the base layer (non-patterned region) of the LMO electrode and LiPON SE, respectively, and h_{Pattern} represents the height of the patterned region for the patterned design. s_0 , s_1 , and s_2 indicate the interfaces between the positive current collector and positive electrode, positive electrode and SE, and negative electrode and SE, respectively.

Figure 1(a) depicts the schematic representation of the planar configuration, while Figure 1(b) depicts the patterned configurations of the interface design geometry. The black arrows highlight the electrode/SE interfaces, s_1 at the positive electrode/SE interface and s_2 at the negative electrode/SE interface. In a planar geometry configuration (Figure 1(a)), the electrode/SE interface has a uniform dimension for the electrochemical reaction to occur across the entire interface. The components, like the electrodes and SE, are arranged in a flat layer where the height/thickness of each component is uniform. On the other hand, the patterned configuration (Figure 1(b)) has non-uniform electrode/SE interface dimensions across the entire interface, which differentiates from planar geometry. Unlike the uniform planar configuration, this design introduces geometric complexity that mimics particle-level irregularities, enabling more realistic simulation of ion transport and interfacial behavior. As such, it serves as a critical step between idealized thin films and the complex architectures of composite ASSLIBs, improving both physical relevance and model transferability. Thus, this design enables a systematic investigation of non-planar structures with controlled and reproducible features to study the structure-performance relationship in battery performance. It can measure geometric parameters such as height and spacing correctly, which are directly correlated with performance.

2. 2 General Modeling Frameworks and Assumptions

In this study, two physics-based modeling frameworks based on dynamic parametrization were formulated: (i) an electrochemical model and (ii) a fully coupled electrochemical–mechanical model to quantitatively compare their predictive accuracy in simulating the behavior and gain insight into ASSLIB behavior. Within these modeling frameworks, non-porous electrodes are used. We utilize LiMn_2O_4 (LMO) as a positive electrode material, LiPON as SE, and Li metal as a negative electrode. The general assumptions underlying the models are as follows.

1. All material domains (electrodes and SE) are assumed to be homogeneous and isotropic.
2. Isothermal conditions are maintained throughout the simulation domain.
3. Charge neutrality is assumed in the SE, with an electroneutral bulk and no space charge regions.
4. Perfect interfacial contact is assumed between all layers (electrode–SE and electrode–current collector), with no delamination or void formation.
5. Side reactions (e.g., positive electrode–SE interphase formation, CEI) are excluded.

6. Electrode and SE materials are considered linear elastic in the electro-chemo-mechanical model.

2.3 Governing Equations

2.3.1 Electrochemical Model

The electrochemical model, formulated within an uncoupled framework, exclusively captures the fundamental electrochemical processes governing lithium-ion transport, charge conservation, and electrochemical reaction kinetics within electrodes and SE, explicitly excluding mechanical effects. This uncoupled framework focuses on solving a nonlinear partial differential equation that describes the spatiotemporal evolution of lithium concentration, electrostatic potentials, and interfacial charge transfer. These governing equations are provided below.

Electrochemical reaction at the electrode/SE interface

An electrochemical reaction occurs at the electrode/SE interface during the charge-discharge process, where Li^+ is inserted into or extracted from the host electrode material. In this work, a perfect contact at the interface is assumed.

The electrochemical reaction at the positive electrode/SE interface is expressed as

In this reaction, x represents the fraction of lithium ions involved in the process. During charging, lithium ions are extracted from the positive electrode material and move towards the negative electrode, while electrons flow through the external circuit. During discharging, the process is reversed, with lithium ions inserted back into the positive electrode material.

The rate of electrochemical reaction at the positive electrode/SE interface (s_1 in Figure 1) is obtained using the extended Butler-Volmer kinetics equation, which considers the influence of mechanical stress as follows.

$$j_{s_1} = j_{0,s_1} \left(\exp \left[\frac{\alpha_{\text{pos}} F \eta}{RT} \right] - \exp \left[- \frac{(1 - \alpha_{\text{pos}}) F \eta}{RT} \right] \right) \quad (2)$$

$$j_{0,s_1} = F * K_{\text{pos}} \left(\left[\frac{(C_{\text{Li,max}} - C_{\text{Li}}) * C_{\text{Li}^+}}{(C_{\text{Li,max}} - C_{\text{Li,min}}) * C_{\text{tot}}} \right]^{\alpha_{\text{pos}}} * \left[\frac{(C_{\text{Li}} - C_{\text{Li,min}})}{(C_{\text{Li,max}} - C_{\text{Li,min}})} \right]^{1 - \alpha_{\text{pos}}} \right) \quad (3)$$

Where j_{s_1} and j_{0,s_1} represent the current density and exchange current density (A m^{-2}) at interface s_1 , K_{pos} is the reaction rate constant ($\text{mol m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$), α_{pos} is the charge transfer coefficient, C_{Li} is the concentration of lithium (mol m^{-3}), $C_{\text{Li,max}}$ is the maximum lithium concentration (mol m^{-3}), $C_{\text{Li,min}}$ is the minimum lithium concentration (mol m^{-3}), and η is the overpotential in the positive electrode (V) whereas the C_{Li^+} and C_{tot} represents the concentrations of Li^+ and total lithium concentration in the SE, respectively, (mol m^{-3}). Similarly, R is the ideal gas constant ($8.314 \text{ J mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$), T is the absolute temperature (K), and F is the Faraday constant ($96485.3 \text{ C mol}^{-1}$). The variable j_{0,s_1} is defined based on the work of Fathiannasab et al. [39]. In this work, the maximum and minimum lithium concentrations ($C_{\text{Li,max}}$, $C_{\text{Li,min}}$) are defined based on the SoD range chosen for the simulation. Specifically, the simulation is conducted over the SoD window between 0.01 and 0.99, where $C_{\text{Li,min}}$ corresponds to the lower SoD bound multiplied by the reference lithium concentration of LMO, C_{ref} ($22860 \text{ (mol m}^{-3})$) [40]. Similarly, $C_{\text{Li,max}}$ corresponds to the higher SoD bound multiplied by the C_{ref} .

The overpotential is defined as the difference between the applied voltage ($\Phi_{S, pos} - \Phi_{SE}$), and equilibrium potential (E_{eq}).

$$\eta = \Phi_{S, pos} - \Phi_{SE} - E_{eq} \quad (4)$$

where Φ_{SE} (V) is the electric potential in LiPON and $\Phi_{S, pos}$ is the electric potential (V) of the positive electrode. E_{eq} depends on the SoD, which relates the electrode potential to the lithium content (SoD) within the electrode.

On the other hand, in this model, pure lithium metal is utilized as a negative electrode, serving as a continuous ion reservoir. Thus, we exclude a detailed representation of this electrode, assuming a high electrical conductivity and low modulus, focusing instead on the charge transfer kinetics occurring at the interface of the positive electrode with SE.

Transport processes in the LiPON solid electrolyte

The SE behavior is modeled using the Nernst–Planck equation along with the electroneutrality condition, as demonstrated in the work of Cabras et al.^[41] and Rajmakers et al.^[36], to capture the ion transport phenomena that effectively simulate ion diffusion and migration as follows.

$$\mathbf{J}_i = -D_i \nabla C_i + \frac{z_i F D_i C_i \nabla \Phi_{SE}}{RT} \quad (5)$$

Where \mathbf{J}_i is the molar flux of species i ($\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$), D_i is the diffusion coefficient of species i ($\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$), C_i is concentrations of species i (mol m^{-3}) and z_i is the charge number of species i , with i corresponding to either cations, Li^+ or anions, X^- , as determined by the binary dissociation of the LiPON SE.

Transport processes in the electrode

Lithium transport in electrode phases is governed only by solid-state diffusion, under the assumption that Li charge is fully shielded, thereby neglecting the migration (drift) term. The concentration of lithium in the electrode material is thus calculated based on mass conservation equations:

$$\frac{\partial C_{Li}}{\partial t} = -\nabla \cdot \mathbf{J}_{Li} \quad (6)$$

Where t is the lithiation time (s), and \mathbf{J}_{Li} is the molar flux of lithium ions ($\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$). During the lithium insertion/extraction process, lithium inside the electrode material is driven by the electrochemical potential gradient $\nabla \mu_{Li}$ (J mol^{-1}). Hence, \mathbf{J}_{Li} is determined as

$$\mathbf{J}_{Li} = -M_{Li} \nabla \mu_{Li} \quad (7)$$

Where M_{Li} is the mobility of Li^+ in the electrode material, which is defined using the Nernst-Einstein relation as:

$$M_{Li} = \frac{D_{Li}}{RT} \quad (8)$$

Where D_{Li} is the diffusion coefficient of lithium in the positive electrode active material ($\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$). The electrochemical potential of lithium ion, μ_{Li} , is expressed as

$$\mu_{Li} = \mu_0 + RT \ln(C_{Li}) \quad (9)$$

where μ_0 represents the chemical potential in the standard state. The gradient under a constant temperature is:

$$\nabla \mu_{Li} = RT \frac{\nabla C_{Li}}{C_{Li}} \quad (10)$$

Substituting Equation (10) and Equation (8) into Equation (7), J_{Li} can be rewritten as

$$J_{Li} = -D_{Li}\nabla C_{Li} \quad (11)$$

Furthermore, combining Equation (11) with the mass conservation Equation (6) gives the final governing equation expressed as:

$$\frac{\partial C_{Li}}{\partial t} = D_{Li}\nabla^2 C_{Li} \quad (12)$$

The local electric current density $j_{Li, pos}$ ($A\ m^{-2}$) in the positive electrode is calculated using Ohm's law:

$$j_{Li, pos} = k\nabla\Phi_{S, pos} \quad (13)$$

Where k denotes the electrical conductivity ($S\ m^{-1}$). The $j_{Li, pos}$ is calculated based on the charge balance equation:

$$\nabla \cdot j_{Li, pos} = 0 \quad (14)$$

Notably, the model incorporates a concentration-dependent lithium diffusivity in the positive electrode, which is crucial for accurately capturing the non-linear transport phenomena observed in solid-state batteries. Despite excluding mechanical strain and stress effects from lithiation, this uncoupled framework offers a multiscale representation of ion transport and interfacial reaction kinetics to predict battery behavior across a range of operating conditions. This uncoupled framework serves as a baseline for subsequent comparison with fully coupled electro-chemo-mechanical models that additionally consider stress-induced phenomena impacting battery performance.

2.3.2 Fully Coupled Electrochemical-Mechanical Model

The fully coupled electro-chemo-mechanical model integrates lithium-ion transport, charge conservation, and reaction kinetics with mechanical deformation and stress evolution in battery electrodes and SE. This model extends the electrochemical framework by incorporating mechanical equilibrium and constitutive relations that describe electro-chemo-mechanical coupling. Unlike uncoupled models, it explicitly captures the two-way coupling whereby lithiation-induced volume changes generate stresses that impact ion transport and electrochemical reactions.

The lithium transport and the generated stress are described by Li^+ concentration and Cauchy stress variables, respectively. The gradient of Li^+ concentration resulting from the electrochemical process significantly impacts the mechanical response of the ASSLIB materials, which governs the dynamic evolution of stress and strain. Simultaneously, the generated mechanical stress influences the electrochemical process, thereby impacting the evolution of Li^+ concentration. This coupling of electrochemistry and mechanics drives the spatiotemporal evolution of both Li^+ concentration and stress. This theory forms a foundation for this physics-based computational modeling. Thus, this section outlines the mathematical equations governing our model, developed based on the methodology detailed in our previous study^[33], to effectively simulate the behavior of thin film ASSLIBs.^[36,42]

In this fully coupled model, the materials of the ASSLIB are assumed to be isotropic and exhibit linear elasticity under quasi-static deformation. Therefore, the mechanical deformation gradient observed in the materials is calculated based on the quasi-static conservation of linear momentum, defined as:

$$\nabla \cdot \sigma = 0 \quad (15)$$

Where σ is the Cauchy stress tensor (Pa), which encompasses two distinct components: the elastic stress and the diffusion-induced stress.

$$\sigma = \frac{E_{pos}}{[(1+\nu)]} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} + \frac{E_{pos}\nu}{[(1+\nu)(1-2\nu)]} (\text{tr}\boldsymbol{\varepsilon})\mathbf{I} + \frac{E_{pos}}{(1-2\nu)} \frac{\Omega}{3} (C_{Li} - C_{Li,0})\mathbf{I} \quad (16)$$

Where E_{pos} is Young's modulus (Pa), ν is Poisson's ratio, $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ strain tensor, Ω is partial molar volume of lithium ($\text{m}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$) and $C_{Li,0}$ is the initial lithium-ion concentration (mol m^{-3}) in the positive electrode, and \mathbf{I} is identity tensor. The Young's modulus is treated as a dynamic parameter that evolves with changes in state of charge conditions, crucial for accurately capturing the evolving behavior of the material. $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ given by:

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} = \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)(\nabla\mathbf{u} + \nabla\mathbf{u}^T) \quad (17)$$

Where $\nabla\mathbf{u}$ is the gradient of the displacement vector \mathbf{u} .

Transport processes and reaction kinetics remain governed by the equations from the electrochemical model but include stress-dependent modifications to diffusivity and overpotential, reflecting the electrochemo-mechanical coupling. The reaction current density j_{s_1} in the extended Butler–Volmer equation, Equation 2, is modified to include the stress-dependent overpotential. The overpotential, Equation 4, is revised to include the effect of mechanical stress, particularly potential-induced stress ($\frac{\Omega\nabla\sigma_h}{F}$), calculated as:

$$\eta = \Phi_{S, pos} - \Phi_{SE} - E_{eq} - \frac{\Omega\nabla\sigma_h}{F} \quad (18)$$

where σ_h is hydrostatic stress (Pa), which is the average stress experienced by the electrode material, calculated by summing the normal stresses in the principal directions and dividing by 3:

$$\sigma_h = \text{tr}\left(\frac{\sigma}{3}\right) \quad (19)$$

Where the $\text{tr}(\sigma)$ refers to the trace of the Cauchy stress tensor, σ , representing the sum of its normal (diagonal) components.

$$\text{tr}(\sigma) = \sigma'_{xx} + \sigma'_{yy} + \sigma'_{zz} \quad (20)$$

where σ'_{xx} , σ'_{yy} , and σ'_{zz} are the normal stresses (Pa) in the x, y, and z directions, respectively. This and all other tensorial summations are expressed using the Einstein summation convention, unless otherwise specified.

Additionally, the lithium transport in the electrode is governed by mass conservation as in the uncoupled electrochemical model but driven by a stress-dependent electrochemical potential, μ_{Li} , expressed as:

$$\mu_{Li} = \mu_0 + RT\ln(C_{Li}) - \Omega\sigma_h \quad (21)$$

At constant temperature, this μ_{Li} is expressed as:

$$\nabla\mu_{Li} = RT \frac{\nabla C_{Li}}{C_{Li}} - \nabla(\Omega\sigma_h) \quad (22)$$

Consequently, lithium flux, J_{Li} , and concentration evolution are expressed as:

$$J_{Li} = -D_{Li} \left[\nabla C_{Li} - \frac{\Omega C_{Li}}{RT} \nabla \sigma_h \right] \quad (23)$$

$$\frac{\partial C_{Li}}{\partial t} = D_{Li} \left[\nabla^2 C_{Li} - \frac{\Omega}{RT} \nabla C_{Li} \cdot \nabla \sigma_h - \frac{\Omega C_{Li}}{RT} \nabla^2 \sigma_h \right] \quad (24)$$

σ_h and C_{Li} ensure the coupling between the electrochemical process and the mechanical response of the electrode material.

2.4 Model simulation conditions

Both experimentally and computationally, the electrochemical cell was subjected to a galvanostatic discharge process under a temperature-controlled condition of 25°C. For the fully coupled model, the integration of lithium transport and mechanical response involves a complex interplay between electrochemical reactions, material properties, and geometric constraints. The lithium transport affects the mechanical response through concentration-induced volume changes and interfacial reactions, while the mechanical constraints and stress distributions can, in turn, influence the lithium transport pathways and kinetics. However, in the pure electrochemical model, mechanical effects are ignored and assumed to have a negligible impact.

Thus, to solve the above governing equations, appropriate boundary and initial conditions are applied, with the negative electrode serving as an unlimited lithium source. Thus, the main constraints are at the interfaces, the positive electrode, SE, and the initial lithium content within each phase.

i. Initial conditions

a) Electrochemical

- Uniform lithium concentration is set in each domain

$$C_{Li}(t=0) = C_{Li,0} = C_{Li,min} \quad (25)$$

$$C_{Li^+}(t=0) = C_{Li^+,0} \quad (26)$$

Where $C_{Li,0}$ and $C_{Li^+,0}$ are the initial lithium concentration at the positive electrode and SE, respectively.

- Electric Potential:

The negative electrode potential ($\Phi_{S, neg}$) at the negative electrode/SE interface (s_2 in Figure 1), is set to 0 V versus SHE, serving as reference potential.

$$\Phi_{S, neg}(s_2, t) = 0 \quad (27)$$

b) Mechanical

- No Displacement/Stress/Strain profiles across the whole solid region, ensuring the cell starts from a stress-free baseline.

$$\mathbf{u}(t=0) = 0, \quad \boldsymbol{\sigma}(t=0) = 0, \quad \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(t=0) = 0 \quad (28)$$

ii. Boundary conditions:

a) Electrochemical

- Flux condition at interface s_1

$$n \cdot \nabla C_{Li}(s_1) = \frac{-j_{s_1}}{D_{Li} F} \quad (29)$$

where n is the derivative in the direction normal to the boundary.

- Zero flux condition on outer boundaries

At the outer boundaries (s_0 , and s_2 in Figure 1) and edges (left and right), there is no net lithium flux across the boundaries:

$$n \cdot \nabla C_{Li} \text{ (outer boundaries)} = 0 \quad (30)$$

- Galvanostatic current condition
a constant current density, j_{app} , is applied at the positive electrode/SE interface, s_1 .

b) Mechanical

- Fixed boundary condition
Displacements at the negative electrode/SE interface (s_2 in Figure 1) and at the positive electrode/positive current collector interface (s_0 in Figure 1) are constrained to prevent rigid body motion and to represent mechanical constraints applied during cell testing.

$$\mathbf{u}(x, y = s_0, t) = 0, \quad \mathbf{u}(x, y = s_2, t) = 0 \quad (31)$$

Similarly, symmetry and edge conditions are applied on the sides where no displacement change is introduced.

- Normal free boundary condition
Displacement changes only occur at the positive electrode/LiPON interface, s_1 . Thus, the displacement at interface (s_1 in Figure 1) is free (unconstrained) in both the horizontal and vertical direction,

$$\mathbf{u}_x(s_1, t) = free, \quad \mathbf{u}_y(s_1, t) = Free \quad (32)$$

All the above governing equations, different boundaries, and initial conditions are implemented and solved in the COMSOL Multiphysics® software version 6.2. The computational domain was discretized using a 2D finite element mesh consisting of 5600 elements. The resulting discretized system of equations, governing ionic transport, electrochemical kinetics, and mechanical deformation, was solved using the Parallel Direct Sparse Solver (PARDISO) provided in the commercial COMSOL Multiphysics® software. A fully coupled approach was employed, whereby all relevant field variables were solved simultaneously within each time step to maintain strong multi-physical interactions. Temporal integration was performed using a second-order backward differentiation formula (BDF2), ensuring robust and accurate time stepping for stiff, nonlinear systems. All material parameters used in the simulation, unless explicitly stated otherwise, are listed in Table 2.

Table 2: Model parameters used in the simulation

Parameter	Value [Units]	Description	Reference	
Planar geometry	h_{LMO}	90 [nm]	LMO layer thickness	Experimental
	h_{LiPON}	50 [nm]	LiPON Layer thickness	Experimental
LMO electrode	Ω	3.49e-6 [m ³ mol ⁻¹]	Partial molar volume of Li ⁺ in LMO	[40]
	C_{ref}	22860 [molm ⁻³]	Maximum lithium concentration of LMO	[40]
	ν_{LMO}	0.3	LMO Poisson Ratio	[40]
	D_{Li}	Varying based on SoD	Diffusion coefficient of Li ⁺ in LMO	[33]
	E_{Li}	Varying based on SoD	Young Modulus of LMO	[33]
LiPON solid	δ	0.18	Fraction of free Li-ions in equilibrium	[25]
	K_r	8.00e-7 [m ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹]	Li-ion recombination rate	[36]

electrolyt e	D_{n^-}	5.69e-16 [m ² s ⁻¹]	Diffusion coefficient for uncompensated negative charges in LiPON	[36]
	D_{Li^+}	1.73e-16 [m ² s ⁻¹]	Diffusion coefficient for Li-ion in LiPON electrolyte	[36]
	C_{tot}	6.01e4 [mol m ⁻³]	The total concentration of ions in the LiPON matrix	[36]
	v_{LiPON}	0.25	LiPON Poisson Ratio	[42]
	ρ_{LiPON}	2300 [kg m ⁻³]	density of LiPON	[43,44]
	E_{LiPON}	77 [GPa]	LiPON Young Modulus	[42]
	Z_{Li^+}	+1	Charge of lithium-ion in LiPON	
	Z_{n^-}	-1	Charge of uncompensated negative charges in LiPON	
Others	α_{pos}	0.50	Charge transfer coefficient, positive electrode	[36]
	α_{neg}	0.50	Charge transfer coefficient, negative electrode	[36]

3. Experimental Section

Electrode preparation

LMO thin films were deposited via radio frequency magnetron sputtering using a Kurt J. Lesker Company sputtering tool (Mini SPECTROS/Nano 36 glovebox) that was installed inside an Ar-filled glovebox. The substrate consisted of a Si wafer with 300 nm of thermally grown SiO₂, coated with 10 nm of TiO₂, and covered with ~100 nm of Pt as a current collector. Once the substrates were loaded inside the tool, the chamber was pumped down to a high vacuum (1 × 10⁻⁷ Torr) and then stabilized at a pressure of 10 mTorr using Ar. Using a forward power of 45 W, the Ar plasma was ignited, and the pressure was adjusted to 3 mTorr for deposition. The power was ramped up to 70 W at 0.033 W/s, followed by 30 minutes of pre-sputtering. During this time, impurities on the surface of the target were removed, while the sample was covered by a metallic shutter. After the pre-sputtering process, the shutter was opened to begin the deposition onto the substrates. LMO was sputtered for 2h and 8h for a target thickness of 90 nm and 350 nm, respectively. During the deposition, the sample was continuously rotated at a speed of 20 RPM to ensure uniform film growth. To finalize the deposition, the sample shutter was closed, and the power was ramped down to 45 W at 0.033 W/s before the plasma was turned off. The samples were left under high vacuum for 30 minutes before venting the deposition chamber.

After sputtering, the samples were annealed in a silicon carbide SiC susceptor using an Annealsys As-One rapid thermal-processing (RTP) system at 700 °C for 1h under an oxygen atmosphere.

LMO was patterned on top of an annealed basal blanket of 90 nm LMO using contact lithography and the lift-off technique. The patterns were defined using contact lithography as follows: First, the substrates were coated with LOR1A lift-off resist (MicroChem) by spin coating at 2000 RPM for 30 seconds. The coated samples were baked on a hot plate at 190°C for 5 minutes. Second, the samples were coated with a positive photoresist IX845G (JSR Micro NV) by spin coating at 4000 RPM for 30 s and baked for 1 minute at 120°C. After each baking step, the samples were cooled down on an aluminum plate for 1 minute before further processing. Third, the samples were exposed in a Karl Suss MA6 mask aligner using a photomask that consisted of transparent glass with patterns made of opaque chromium, designed in-house, and fabricated by Photonics (UK) LTD. The samples were then exposed

to a light intensity of 55.2 mW/cm^2 for 3 s. Finally, the samples were developed using OPD5262 (Fujifilm) by submerging them in the solution for 1 minute. The developer etched away the exposed photoresist (uncovered from the mask). The samples were then rinsed in a bath of ultra-pure water with continuous flow until the resistivity of water reached $10 \text{ M}\Omega\cdot\text{cm}$. The samples were dried using a N_2 gun and inspected under an optical microscope. After the patterns were defined on the photoresist, LMO was sputtered for 8h, filling the patterns made by lithography. Once LMO was deposited on top of the sample with a patterned resist, the sample was immersed in a beaker containing Microstrip 2001 (Fujifilm) at 80°C for lift-off. This solvent removed all the resist on the sample and left only the material that was in direct contact with the LMO basal blanket. After 30 minutes, the beaker containing the solution and samples was placed in an ultrasonic bath (Elmasonic P, Elma) filled with water, set at 55°C for 5 minutes at 37 kHz. The samples were then transferred to a beaker containing IPA and sonicated for 5 minutes under the same conditions, and the samples were rinsed with ultrapure water and dried under N_2 . Finally, the patterned samples were annealed under the same conditions.

Patterned LMO films were coated with LiPON using the same sputtering system equipped with a Li_3PO_4 target (Lesker). Plasma was ignited at a pressure of 10 mTorr with an initial power of 45 W, which was gradually increased to 70 W at a ramp rate of 0.033 W/s. Nitrogen was introduced into the Ar carrier gas to facilitate the formation of LiPON. The deposition time was optimized, targeting a layer thickness of 50 nm. All deposition steps were carried out inside an Ar-filled glovebox to prevent contamination.

Physical characterization

Surface morphology of the samples was characterized using a FEI Nova 200 field emission scanning electron microscope (FE-SEM). Imaging was performed in high-vacuum mode using the secondary electron (SE) detector. An accelerating voltage of 3 or 5 kV was used, with a working distance of 4.9 mm.

Electrochemical experiments

LMO was measured using a custom-built three-electrode Teflon cell. The cell consisted of two vertical channels, each with one opening at the top and only one with an opening at the bottom. Both channels were connected using a horizontal capillary close to the sample for ion exchange. The LMO working electrode was fixed at the bottom's opening using a metallic clamp. A DuPont Kalrez O-ring was placed between the cell and thin film to seal the junction and prevent electrolyte leakage. The measured exposed area, defined by the O-ring, was approximately 0.785 cm^2 . Lithium ribbons were used as counter and reference electrodes, where the former was placed in the channel above the sample, and the latter was placed in the channel with a single opening. The electrolyte used was prepared by dissolving LiClO_4 (battery grade, dry, 99.99%, Sigma Aldrich) in propylene carbonate (PC) (anhydrous, Sigma-Aldrich). The measurements were performed using a Multi Autolab/M101 potentiostat (Metrohm) connected to the cell inside an Ar-filled MBraun glovebox with O_2 and H_2O content of $< 0.1 \text{ ppm}$.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1 Predictive accuracy of models

The accuracy of physics-based simulations for lithium-ion and beyond batteries critically depends on the description of physics level, coupling effects, and parameter assumptions. In our previous study, we analyzed the influence of parameter assumption and Multiphysics coupling level on model accuracy by benchmarking static parameter assumptions against partially coupled dynamic models, where either

kinetics or mechanical parameters are dynamic (SoD dependent), and fully coupled dynamic models with both properties are dynamic. Static assumptions, neglecting the continuous evolution of lithium transport and mechanical responses during battery operation, lead to significant performance prediction errors, often on the order of tens of percent. In contrast, a fully coupled dynamic parameterization shows the capability to accurately reproduce the data observed in experiments. These findings underscore the necessity of incorporating dynamic, physically realistic parameters to reliably predict all-solid-state battery performance.

Extending from this foundation, to quantify the impact of the levels of Multiphysics description on predictive accuracy, we conduct a comparative assessment between a dynamic electrochemical model, an uncoupled framework, and a fully coupled framework, a dynamic fully coupled electro-chemo-mechanical model. For the uncoupled framework, we use the SoD-dependent diffusion coefficient of lithium in the LMO electrode, while for the fully coupled framework additionally incorporate the SoD-dependent Young's modulus of the LMO electrode. Notably, the SoD-dependent diffusion coefficient of lithium in the LMO and its Young's modulus were obtained from our previous study^[33]. To ensure a direct comparison, both models are constructed using the same geometry (planar design) and mesh configurations. To carefully compare and validate the models, a well-defined and precisely controlled experiment was conducted using a Pt/LMO/LiPON thin film as the working electrode, with model parameters detailed in Table 2, unless otherwise specified. Notably, the same C rate, as used in the galvanostatic charge-discharge experiment, 1C rate, is implemented in the simulation.

Thus, to assess the reliability and accuracy of the models, we conducted a thorough comparison of simulated voltage profiles with experimental data, including quantitative analysis of discharge potential versus capacity. The specific volumetric capacity (mAh/cm^3) is determined by dividing the calculated capacity by the electrode volume, V (m^3).

Figure 2: Comparison of discharge curve predicted from the simulation of the dynamic fully coupled electrochemical-mechanical model (red solid lines), dynamic electrochemical model (red dashed lines), and experimental data (blue solid lines) at room temperature using a planar cell configuration with a

Pt/LMO/LiPON electrode for model validation. The x-axis unit mAh/cm³ represents the volumetric capacity, which quantifies charge storage normalized to electrode volume.

Figure 2 illustrates the discharge curve obtained from the experiment and predicted from both models for the LMO-based thin-film electrode. The figure shows the electrode potential versus discharge capacity, comparing predictions from the uncoupled framework, dynamic electrochemical model (red dashed lines), and dynamic fully coupled electro-chemo-mechanical models, fully coupled framework (red solid line), with experimental data (blue solid line). Using the uncoupled model, it is observed that at the end of discharge time, the discharge capacity was overestimated by 26.5% relative to the experimental value. This large deviation results from neglecting non-linear and localized effects driven by mechanical stress during operation. This overestimation implies an overvaluation of battery performance and lifetime, leading to several consequences such as accelerated battery degradation, resulting in quick battery decline and even unexpected device failure. This finding shows that only the electrochemical framework description fails to capture the practical complex behavior of a thin film system, resulting in substantial errors in performance predictions.

On the other hand, the fully coupled framework provides more accurate predictions compared to the uncoupled framework. The fully coupled framework exhibits a strong agreement with the experimentally measured discharge curve, showing less than 0.5% discharge capacity deviation at the end of discharge time. This close alignment underscores the capability of a fully coupled electro-chemo-mechanical model to capture the complex dynamic behavior within the battery system. The incorporation of mechanical phenomena and dynamic parameters, such as SoD dependent diffusion coefficients and Young's modulus, contributes to this enhanced accuracy.

These results emphasize the crucial role of incorporating detailed Multiphysics descriptions and dynamic parameterization in predictive battery models to accurately capture complex, coupled phenomena governing performance and degradation. Uncoupled, electrochemical models exhibit limited accuracy due to their inability to describe phenomena beyond electrochemical processes. By extending these models with mechanical coupling (full coupled electro-chemo-mechanical model), the framework captures mechanical effects such as stress-induced degradation and spatial non-uniformities in mechanical stress and concentration gradients. Thus, integrating electrochemical and mechanical phenomena with SoD-dependent parameters enables unprecedented fidelity in simulating realistic operating conditions. This comprehensive approach not only achieves accurate reproduction of experimental data but also enhances predictive reliability, providing essential insights for optimizing battery design, safety, and management strategies rooted in fundamental physics.

Thus, with the coupled model successfully validated, it is then extended to quantify the impact of electrode microstructure variations on the overall performance and degradation of thin film electrodes. In particular, to quantitatively evaluate the interplay between microstructural heterogeneity, transport processes, and mechanical effects, providing detailed insights into factors that limit battery efficiency and long-term stability.

4.2 Effect of electrode/SE interface morphology

In the realm of lithium-ion and beyond lithium batteries, the geometrical configuration of their electrode–electrolyte interface plays a pivotal role in determining overall performance^[45–47]. This interface geometry directly affects ion transport pathways and the electrochemical utilization of the active material, while also influencing the evolution of mechanical stresses during operation. Thus, to

explore, investigate, and understand the effect of interface geometrical structure on the thin film performance, the validated fully coupled electro-chemo-mechanical model is utilized.

In this study, planar (Figure 1(a)) and patterned (Figure 1(b)) Li/LiPON/LMO cell geometries are benchmarked to assess the role of electrode/SE geometrical configuration in battery behavior. To ensure direct comparability, the patterned and planar geometries were simulated with identical cell volumes (the same total cell height and length) and equivalent mesh discretization. In the patterned design, the pattern height-to-pattern base layer height ratio was set at 0.2 for benchmarking. The comparison focuses on the spatial distributions of lithium concentration and mechanical stress within the LMO positive electrode adopted throughout the study. These profiles directly determine ionic transport efficiency, electrochemical utilization, mechanical stability, and degradation.

Figure 3: Spatial distribution of lithium concentration and mechanical stress across the planar (a and b) and patterned (c and d) LMO electrode configurations at the end of discharge time (EoD). (a, b) Distribution of lithium concentration across the electrode thickness within the planar cell (a) and patterned cell (b). (c, d) distribution of mechanical stress across the thickness within the planar cell (c) and patterned cell (d). Position along thickness (vertical axis) starts from within the bottom positive electrode and extends into the positive electrode/ SE interface layer. The color-coded curves labelled i, ii, and iii correspond to data extracted from different cross-sections of the structure, as indicated in the inset.

Figure 3 illustrates the distribution of lithium concentration and mechanical stress within the electrode thin film cell for both planar and patterned configurations at the end of discharge time (EoD). EoD represents the time when the electrode potential reaches the lower cutoff threshold (3.4 V), indicating the completion of the discharge cycle. Figure 3 (a) presents the distribution of lithium concentration within the planar cell. The plot shows uniform lithium concentration along the length (in-plane direction) of the electrode, indicating the absence of lateral concentration gradients compared to the across electrode thickness direction. In contrast, across the electrode thickness, it exhibits pronounced spatial heterogeneity, with the lithium concentration varying significantly.

Comparing this finding to the patterned configuration, the impact of the pattern design on lithium distribution is shown in Figure 3(b). It demonstrates that lithium concentration varies significantly across the electrode thickness and along electrode length (in-plane distribution), unlike the planar geometry case. This is attributed to the difference in the interface design, as it directly affects the contact area and ion transport pathways at the interface. The patterned design has a non-uniform positive electrode thickness, thus a non-uniform distance between the negative electrode and the positive electrode. This results in different diffusion length pathways for Li^+ transport and electrochemical reaction rates within the positive electrode, leading to heterogeneous Li^+ distribution throughout the bulk electrode.

These simulation results underscore that lithium concentration gradients are predominantly localized across the electrode thickness for both design configurations (Figure 3 (a and b)). However, they differ in the lithium concentration gradients and distribution along the length of the electrode cell (Figure 3 (a) vs Figure 3 (b)). This difference stems from variations in the interface geometry. The planar design has a uniform SE/electrode thickness, hence a uniform distance between the negative and positive electrodes, resulting in uniform Li^+ distributions along the cell length. This is mainly due to the uniform dimensions of the SE, where Li^+ diffuses equally and reaches the electrode/SE interface at the same rate, resulting in the same Li^+ diffusion pathways throughout the bulk electrode. However, the non-uniform distance between the negative and positive electrodes in the patterned design leads to non-uniform Li^+ distributions along the cell length. These findings demonstrate that the inhomogeneity of the interface along the length leads to nonuniform Li^+ distributions in the electrode domain.

To explore this further, an in-depth analysis of the effects of electrode geometry on mechanical stress distribution in regions of the positive electrode is carried out.

Figure 3 (c) shows the distribution of mechanical stress within the planar cell. It depicts that the spatial distribution of mechanical stress in the planar design is non-uniform across the thickness of the positive electrode. This phenomenon is attributed to the consequences of non-uniform lithium distribution across the thickness electrode observed in Figure 3 (a). Additionally, Figure 3 (c) presents a uniform mechanical stress-profile along the electrode length (in-plane direction) at a different cross-section. This highlights that a high gradient occurs across the thickness of the electrode, while a minimal /no gradient occurs along its length. This finding is compared to a patterned design configuration.

Figure 3 (d) illustrates the distribution of mechanical stress in the bulk surface of the positive electrode for the patterned design configuration. It illustrates that mechanical stress, like lithium distribution in pattern design, depends on the thickness/position of the positive electrode. The patterned configuration resulted in a higher magnitude of mechanical stress variation across the positive electrode domain than the planar interface design across the positive electrode domain, Figure 3 (c). The planar design shows a stress range of -1.2 GPa to -2 GPa across the electrode (variation ≈ 0.8 GPa; Figure 3 (c)), whereas the pattern design shows -1.2 GPa to -4.2 GPa (variation ≈ 3 GPa; Figure 3 (d)).

As depicted in Figure 3(d), the highest (peak) mechanical stress, 4.2 GPa, is observed at/near the edges of the patterned geometry, resulting in higher stress gradient variation near/at the tips/corners of the edges of the pattern. This is mainly due to the presence of lithium concentration gradients within the electrode and a sharp geometric change in the pattern, particularly towards the tips/corners of the edge. The creation of this high stress gradient within the edge and corners of the patterned region indicates a higher risk of mechanical degradation where hotspot areas, such as fractures, cracking, delamination, voiding, etc., of these battery materials can be initiated and propagated. Also, it drives lithium diffusion

due to the coupling effect of electrochemistry and mechanics, leading to a nonuniform lithium concentration distribution across the electrode. This can result in accelerated degradation. This result illustrates that the geometry of the positive electrode has a significant effect on the distribution of lithium and mechanical stress, hence on the performance of ASSLIB.

In addition to Figure 3, illustrating the lithium and mechanical stress distribution at the EoD, indicative of overall transport and kinetics effects, their evolution over discharge time for planar and pattern geometries is shown in the supporting information (SI), SI 1. At the beginning of discharge, both geometries exhibit nearly uniform lithium distributions with minimal stress. As time progresses, concentration gradients and stress levels increase, but remain relatively moderate in the planar electrode. By the end of discharge, the pattern geometry develops pronounced stress hotspots, far higher than in the planar case, highlighting the strong geometry-driven intensification of chemo-mechanical response.

4.3 Validation of Stress Predictions in Patterned Electrodes

The practical electrode microstructure exhibits a complex, heterogeneous geometric arrangement. Here, we use a patterned geometry as an intermediate geometry that bridges simple planar electrodes and complex porous architectures. This design preserves critical features such as spatially varying electrode thickness. This configuration enables precise parametric studies that isolate the influence of specific microstructural characteristics on battery behavior. Consequently, it facilitates mechanistic understanding and quantitative mapping to more complex, experimentally observed phenomena. As shown in Figure 3(d) and Figure SI 1(d), patterned geometries generate pronounced stress gradients throughout the electrode, which correlate directly with crack formation. While these gradients can act as driving forces for lithium redistribution at the particle scale, they simultaneously localize stress and accelerate fracture. These simulation findings demonstrate that irregular interface geometries generate localized heterogeneities in lithium concentration and mechanical stress, acting as hotspots that accelerate degradation. These stress concentrations cause particle fracture, and cracking, disrupting conductive pathways and reducing active material. Additionally, uneven strain leads to loss of contact between battery components, worsening capacity fade and resistance. These coupled chemo-mechanical degradation pathways critically limit battery life and performance, underscoring the importance of microstructural design and mechanical coupling in mitigating failure.

To validate the predictive capability of the continuum fully coupled electro-chemo-mechanical framework findings, we conducted a comparison between simulated and experimental results for a thin film test structure with a solid electrolyte incorporating patterned geometries. To align with the experimental configuration, the same geometric parameters were applied in the simulations. The patterned electrode structure, the electrode base layer was 90 nm with 350 nm pattern height (pattern height-to-pattern base layer height ratio around 4). These dimensions, aligned with the experiments, ensure direct comparison and confirmation of simulation results.

Figure 4. Time-resolved stress evolution in patterned electrodes and experimental validation. (a, b) Simulated stress maps at the beginning (a) and end (b) of discharge. (c, d) SEM images of the pristine electrode (c) and after cycling (d) in the LMO-based thin film electrode stack for the patterned configuration. The stack consists of a silicon substrate with 300 nm of thermally grown SiO₂, coated with a 10 nm TiO₂ layer. A platinum current collector is deposited on top, followed by a patterned LMO film.

Figure 4 (a) presents the development of mechanical stress during discharge and its correspondence with experimentally observed cracking. We find that, whereas the pattern structure is essentially stress-free at the start of discharge (Figure 4 (a)), pronounced stress and stress gradients develop by EOD (Figure 4 (b)). This shows that at EOD, stress is not uniformly distributed but instead becomes highly concentrated at patterned edges. These localized stress maxima represent mechanically vulnerable regions where cracks are most likely to initiate and propagate, producing three main hotspots: at and near pattern edges, within the central pattern region due to constrained expansion, and at the pattern–base junction where geometric discontinuities concentrate strain, which degrades performance. This emphasizes that structural heterogeneity concentrates stress at these critical locations, accelerating localized failure and compromising long-term interfacial integrity. These results highlight how non-planar geometry governs the spatiotemporal evolution of stress.

These predicted hotspots align closely with the experimental observations. SEM imaging of the pristine structure (Figure 4 (c)) shows no evidence of mechanical damage (crack-free), whereas cycled samples after 90 cycles (Figure 4 (d)) exhibit extensive cracking around the pattern edges, within the central pattern region, and at the pattern–base interface, as indicated by the white arrows. This provides a clear qualitative validation of the simulated stress map. This spatial correspondence between simulations and

experiments underscores the predictive capability of the fully coupled framework and highlights geometry-induced stress localization as the main driver of crack initiation in pattern architectures.

Accurate prediction of mechanical failure in ASSLIBs critically depends on capturing the influence of interface geometry on stress distribution. Our simulation framework demonstrates this by closely matching experimental observations, validating its ability to identify locations prone to fracture. Specifically, the spatial correlation between predicted stress concentrations and fracture sites confirms the model's predictive accuracy. Moreover, the model reliably forecasts consistent crack formation patterns and morphologies across the pattern edges and electrode structure. These results highlight the essential role of interface geometry in governing electro-chemo-mechanical behavior and provide mechanistic insights into how bulk geometric features regulate localized mechanical responses during battery operation. Therefore, the simulation framework can be directly applied to evaluate and gain an in-depth understanding of the influence of geometric parameters, such as pattern height, width, and inter-distance, on ASSLIB operation.

4.4 Impact of geometric parameter variations in patterned configuration

Figures (3 and 4) demonstrate that interface geometry significantly affects the electrochemical performance of solid-state batteries by influencing contact area, ion transport pathways, and local stress distributions at the electrode–SE interface. The patterned design exhibits greater mechanical stress gradients than the planar design, suggesting a direct link to possible mechanisms for accelerated degradation and shortening cycle life. In this section, we investigated the sensitivity of several geometrical pattern parameters, including pattern height (H), pattern width (W), and pattern inter-distance (ID), with respect to pattern base layer height (BH) of the patterned positive electrode on the performance of ASSLIBs. The influence of these pattern geometries on the battery performance is investigated by varying their value while keeping other parameters the same. Beyond analyzing lithium distribution and stress distribution profiles, we compared the key performance indicators (KPIs) for various patterned geometric parameters.

In evaluating battery efficiency, two principal KPIs are commonly considered: extraction efficacy and voltaic efficiency. Extraction efficiency, defined as the ratio of the measured discharge capacity to the theoretical maximum capacity, provides a direct and quantitative assessment of how effectively active lithium is utilized within each cell geometry. In contrast, voltaic efficiency, which compares the average discharge voltage to the average charge voltage, primarily captures energy losses due to internal resistance and polarization and is more relevant in full charge–discharge cycling scenarios. While both efficiencies are critical metrics for evaluating ASSLIB performance under galvanostatic conditions, this study focuses exclusively on extraction efficiency as the primary KPI. Since the present analysis is restricted to a discharge cycle, extraction efficiency offers a more pertinent and sensitive measure of electrochemical performance, particularly for distinguishing the impact of geometric variations on lithium utilization.

Thus, the extraction efficiency differences arising from pattern geometry are evaluated using normalized extraction efficiency, which is given by:

$$\text{Normalized extraction efficiency} = \frac{\text{Extraction efficiency}}{\text{Extraction efficiency}_{max}} \quad (33)$$

Where the extraction efficiency η_{\max} refers to the maximum extraction efficiency achievable within the investigated range of pattern geometric parameters. Extraction efficacy is calculated as:

$$\text{Extraction efficiency (\%)} = \frac{\text{Capacity}}{\text{Ideal capacity}} 100 \% \quad (34)$$

The ideal capacity represents the ideal charge output, assuming the electrode is uniformly lithiated to its maximum concentration limit for the given geometry. The capacity of each geometry is normalized by dividing its value by the maximum volumetric capacity observed among pattern geometries, enabling a direct comparison of how efficiently each structure utilizes its available volume. It is crucial to note that throughout the simulation, the lower cutoff threshold voltage was maintained constant, with 99.9% of Li^+ discharge maintained throughout the specified pattern geometry.

The schematic of the considered pattern geometry is illustrated in Figure 5, where only one patterned positive electrode region is considered for analysis. This simplifies the model from the multiple pattern region geometry shown in Figure 1(b) by utilizing the symmetry assumption. The correlation of pattern geometry parameters (H, W, ID, and BH) with electro-chemo-mechanical process and KPIs is analyzed, and a summary of the main trends is provided below.

Figure 5. Schematic representation of selected pattern geometry, showing a single patterned region used for analysis under symmetry assumption.

Figure 6: (a-c) Simulation results showing the distribution of mechanical stress at the EoD for various geometries of pattern height (a), pattern width (b), and pattern inter-distance (c) (with increasing pattern geometric parameters from left to right) of the positive electrode. (d) The sensitivity of normalized extraction efficiency to variations in pattern geometric parameters of the positive electrode.

Figure 6 shows the effect of pattern geometry by independently adjusting the pattern height-to-pattern base layer height ratio for each parameter (H, W, ID) from 0.2 to 6, with all other parameters unchanged. In the height study, only H was varied ($H/BH = 0.2-6$), and the same single-parameter variation

approach was applied to W and ID to isolate their geometric contributions. In Figure 6 (a), the distribution of mechanical stress in the bulk positive electrode at the EoD for various pattern heights is plotted. It is observed that the increase of electrode pattern height (increase of H/HB) induces higher stress not only at/near the edges of the pattern but throughout the patterned region. This indicates that taller pattern height increases stress accumulation within the pattern body while generating steep gradients at the junctions of pattern–base layer, where the electrode step meets the basal layer. These localized stress concentrations establish mechanically vulnerable regions where cracks are likely to initiate/propagate and pattern detachment. This is mainly because with increasing the pattern height, the distance between the short and tall parts of the positive electrode increased, resulting in increased contact region between the patterned part of SE and positive electrode, particularly at the interface of SE/positive electrode along their edges. Nevertheless, these edges represent sites where the highest mechanical stress gradients occur, attributable to sharp geometric changes. In the SI, Figure SI (2) illustrates the effect of pattern height on the distribution of lithium concentration in the positive electrode. We observed that increasing pattern height disrupts the uniformity of lithium-ion transport, yielding progressively heterogeneous concentration fields that reflect localized transport limitations. This non-uniform lithium distribution results in building mechanical stress in the electrode.

Figure 6 (b) demonstrates the mechanical stress generated with various pattern widths at the EoD. As expected, a narrow pattern width has high mechanical stress across the patterned region due to the higher accumulated lithium concentration, as shown in Figure SI (3). Figure SI (3) illustrates the effect of pattern width on lithium concentration distribution in the positive electrode. At narrow widths, restricted spacing between patterns confines ionic transport, leading to lithium accumulation within the patterned region. This uneven distribution coincides with pronounced stress localization at the patterned region, producing sites prone to crack initiation, defect growth, and potential structural failure. This may result in the detachment of the patterned region from its base layer. Thus, the narrower pattern widths can cause the highest risk for mechanical degradation in ASSLIB owing to the limited and restricted space for volume expansion during the discharge process. This limitation creates areas prone to crack initiation/propagation, defect formation, and other mechanical degradations that can even lead to total material failure.

Figure 6 (c) shows the effect of pattern inter-distance (pattern spacing) on stress distributions. It is observed that the stress effect is smaller compared to the influence of pattern height and width (Figure 6 (a) and Figure 6 (b)). At small pattern inter-distances, the positive electrode/SE interface contact area is limited. On the other hand, at larger pattern inter-distances, the interface contact area is large, leading to a greater number of active sites. This results in minimizing the mechanical degradation effect.

The findings of Figure 6 (a to c) illustrate that ASSLIB performance is highly sensitive to pattern geometric parameters. Increasing the pattern height, narrowing the pattern width, and spacing promote crack initiation and propagation, thereby accelerating mechanical degradation. This underscores the critical influence of pattern geometries on the structural integrity and longevity of solid-state batteries.

Figure 6 (d) presents the impact of pattern geometric parameters on the battery's extraction efficiency. It shows efficiency variation with increasing pattern height, width, and inter-distance relative to the pattern base layer height (dimension/BH), highlighting the trade-off between performance and structural integrity in electrode designs. The blue line illustrates the sensitivity of normalized extraction efficiency to pattern height, using the dimensionless parameter of pattern height relative to base layer height. It can be seen that the normalized extraction efficiency decreases with increasing pattern heights, where the H/BH is increasing. At small pattern heights, ionic pathways remain short, which reduces

diffusion path lengths, minimizes concentration polarization, and facilitates uniform ionic transport. This enhances electrode utilization and lowers internal resistance. Conversely, taller patterns prolong diffusion distances, worsening mass transport limitations, which in turn reduce the effective capacity and lower efficiency.

On the other hand, the red line presents the normalized extraction efficiency for various pattern widths, plotted against the dimensionless W/BH . It is observed that the extraction efficiency increases with increasing pattern width, where W/BH increases. Increasing the pattern width increases the contact area of the SE/positive electrode interface by widening the space within the pattern. This increases the effective surface area available for electrochemical reaction, providing more pathways for lithium to diffuse and transport through the positive electrode material. This enhances the capacity and overall battery performance. Furthermore, the green line shows the normalized extraction efficiency for various pattern inter-distance values. It is observed that the efficiency increases with increasing pattern inter-distance. At small pattern inter-distances, the positive electrode/SE interface contact area is limited. On the other hand, at larger pattern inter-distances, the interface contact area is large, leading to a greater number of active sites. This results in high discharge capacity and enhanced efficiency.

Beyond the individual effects of pattern geometric parameters, their relative sensitivities are evaluated to clarify their influence on electrochemical efficiency. As depicted in Figure 6 (d), the impact of pattern height, width, and inter-distance is compared across equivalent variations. It demonstrates that pattern height exhibits the most pronounced effect on efficiency, with a 75 % reduction observed as increasing the pattern height from a baseline ratio of $0.2 \times$ to $6 \times$ of the pattern base layer height value. This substantial decline is mainly attributed to heightened ionic diffusion resistance and polarization, which arise from extended ion transport pathways and limit the utilization of active material. In contrast, variations in pattern width result in a moderate efficiency difference of approximately 20%, reflecting improvements in conductive area and charge transfer mechanisms. Adjustments in pattern inter-distance show the smallest efficiency effect, around 15%, predominantly owing to incremental enhancements in ionic accessibility.

Thus, pattern height emerges as the dominant factor governing both electrochemical performance and mechanical robustness in electrode architectures, consistent with fundamental principles of transport and stress localization. Lower pattern height shortens diffusion pathways and improves active material utilization. Wider electrode patterns ease transport restrictions, resulting in more uniform electrochemical activity and enhanced efficiency. Increasing the spacing of electrode patterns reduces transport constraints, boosting uniform electrochemical activity and system efficiency. These highlight the critical importance of optimizing pattern geometric parameters to preserve the mechanical integrity of solid-state batteries.

5. Conclusion

The performance of ASSLIBs is governed by the complex interactions of their constituent intrinsic interconnected material properties and external operating conditions. For designing and evaluating their performance, gaining an in-depth understanding of these interrelated physico-electro-chemo-mechanical-material- material properties, given their impact on charge transfer, structural stability, and degradation, is crucial. Continuum physics models are essential tools for facilitating a detailed understanding of the relationship between these multifaceted material properties and ASSLIB performance. However, their accurate prediction relies on the detailed description of internal ASSLIB characteristics and careful characterization of model parameters. In this study, we developed and

implemented two modeling frameworks, a simplified approach (electrochemical model) and an advanced, fully coupled electro-chemo-mechanical model, to investigate the behavior of ASSLIBs. Both models were compared with experimental data to assess their predictive accuracy and physical relevance. The electrochemical model overestimates capacity at the end of discharge by 26.5%, reflecting its neglect of mechanical effects such as stress-induced degradation. Conversely, the fully coupled electro-chemo-mechanical model reduces this error to below 0.5 %, accurately capturing the interaction between electrochemical processes and mechanical deformation. This demonstrates the critical importance of incorporating mechanical coupling to precisely predict battery performance and degradation.

Furthermore, in this study, using the experimentally validated fully coupled model, the effect of the electrode/SE interface shape geometry on the performance of ASSLIBs is investigated. Two types of interface geometry, planar (uniform) and patterned (non-uniform) interface geometries, are considered. In planar configurations, the distribution of both lithium concentration and mechanical stress is predominantly governed by their position across the electrode thickness, resulting in 1D gradients. In contrast, patterned configurations exhibit a more complex behavior, with spatial variation of lithium and stress that depends not only on the thickness direction but also across the cell length. This 2D dependence in patterned electrodes leads to heterogeneous distributions and localized regions of high concentration and stress, which can significantly influence electrochemical performance and mechanical reliability. The highest probability for a greater risk of material fracture and failure was induced by utilizing the patterned geometry design instead of the planar interface geometry design, which was confirmed through the experiment. The sharp change in the geometry of the pattern tips/corners and edges is the primary region in which mechanical degradation occurs because the structural heterogeneity (non-uniformity) of the interface geometry significantly influences lithium transport.

In addition, we investigated the influence of various geometric parameters, such as pattern width, pattern height, and pattern inter-distance, to provide complete comparisons and gain more insight into their impact on ASSLIB behavior. It was observed that all these geometrical parameters affect ASSLIB performance. Detachment between the patterned and base layer can occur at large pattern height and narrow pattern width due to the long lithium transport path and high interference between patterns, respectively, during the intercalation process. Similarly, pattern base layer height and pattern inter-distance have critical effects due to the influence of lithium transport, interface contact area, and interference between adjacent patterns. This in-depth investigation provides insights and correlations between pattern geometry and battery performance, offering useful insights for optimization and design considerations.

These findings underscore the detailed description of internal battery behaviors, and correct parameterization plays a crucial role in model accuracy. Moreover, it highlights the critical role of electrode geometry in dictating the spatial profiles of key transport and mechanical phenomena within ASSLIB architectures, specifically in identifying critical areas that can lead to material fracture and failure. Thus, precisely capturing these physico-electro-chemo-mechanical interactions is essential for predictive simulations of degradation mechanisms and performance optimization. This study, however, is limited to the discharge cycle and thin-film architectures, excluding long-term electrochemical degradation mechanisms. Future investigations will incorporate cyclic degradation processes and extend the analysis to composite-based ASSLIBs, thereby advancing the understanding of mechanical durability in practical battery systems.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the website or from the author.

Data Availability

Data will be made available on request.

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